

**MORPHOFUNCTIONAL CHANGES IN THE STOMACH UNDER THE
INFLUENCE OF FOOD DYES (E-171, E-173) AND
THEIR CORRECTION**

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Annotation

Food additives or dyes (E-171, E-173) are substances that are added for technological purposes to give the necessary properties during the production, packaging, transportation or storage of products. E-171 - titanium dioxide is one of the three main materials used in nanotechnology and is used as a colorant and preservative in all medical preparations. Since it is a chemically stable substance, it cannot be broken down by the body, it has low toxicity and biological effect. Some studies have shown that titanium dioxide can cause inflammation in the gut and an increase in free radicals in the tissues, so this substance is stored in the body. This stored substance has the ability to destroy organic particles. In addition, it was found that this dye makes it difficult to absorb some vitamins and minerals. European food safety regulators have declared titanium dioxide unsafe for human consumption due to its potential toxicity.

E173 paints, i.e. give aluminum products a bright silver color. It is used in the production of foil for food. A particularly high concentration of aluminum is observed in canned drinks that are used in the inner packaging of aluminum containers and drinks. There are assumptions that the constant consumption of aluminum in food may be associated with the development of certain diseases, such as various nervous diseases and allergic reactions. In Russia and Ukraine, the

use of the E173 additive in the food industry is prohibited. In addition, E173 dye is banned in Australia and a number of other countries. While most studies suggest that normal amounts of aluminum in food are not harmful to human health, most of these studies have been conducted in animals or in vitro, and more research is needed to evaluate the effects in humans.

Key words: E-171, E-173, preservative, xenobiotic, cytotoxic.

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Морфофункциональные изменения желудка, происходящие под влиянием пищевых красителей (E-171, e-173) и их коррекция.

Аннотация

Пищевые добавки или пищевые красители (E-171, E-173) это вещества, добавляемые в технологических целях для придания продукции необходимых свойств и качеств в процессе производства, упаковки, транспортировки или хранения. Диоксид титана является одним из трех основных материалов, используемых в нанотехнологиях, и в качестве красителя, а также консерванта во всех медицинских препаратах. Поскольку это химически стойкое вещество, оно не может быть расщеплено организмом, имеет низкую токсичность, обладает биологическим действием на организм. Некоторые исследования показали, что диоксид титана может вызывать воспаление в кишечнике и накопление свободных радикалов в тканях, поэтому эти вещества имеют свойство накапливаться в организме. Эти накапливаемые вещества обладают способностью

разрушать организм. Поскольку эти вещества сильно удерживают влагу в организме, тем самым они нарушают водный баланс организма. Кроме того, было обнаружено, что эти красители затрудняют усвоение некоторых витаминов и минералов в организме. Европейские регуляторы безопасности пищевых продуктов определили, что диоксид титана небезопасен для употребления в пищу из-за его потенциальной токсичности.

Краситель E-173 придает алюминиевым изделиям серебристый яркий оттенок. Он используется в производстве фольги для пищевых продуктов. Применяемый во внутренней упаковке алюминиевых бутылок и напитков особенно высокая концентрация алюминия наблюдается в консервированных напитках с истекшим сроком годности. Есть предположения, что постоянное потребление алюминия с пищей может быть связано с развитием определенных заболеваний, таких как болезнь Альцгеймера, различные неврологические расстройства и аллергические реакции. В России и на Украине применение добавки E173 в пищевой промышленности запрещено. Кроме того, краситель E173 запрещен в Австралии и в ряде других стран. Кроме того, хотя исследования показывают, что нормальное количество алюминия в пище не наносит вреда здоровью человека, большинство из этих исследований были проведены на животных и *in vitro*. А для того чтобы проводить испытания на людях необходимы еще более глубокие и доскональные исследования в области науки и развития фармацевтической промышленности.

Ключевые слова: E-171, E-173, консервант, ксенобиотик, цитотоксический.

Relevance of the topic. Currently, some components of food products and most medicines can become xenobiotics and produce harmful substances in the body. They can have an allergenic, mutagenic, carcinogenic or cytotoxic effect. Pollution of water and air on Earth, depletion of natural resources, disruption of

natural processes directly or indirectly affects the human body. Therefore, it is important to analyze the components of food, medicines and tools we use for our needs, to study their effects on the body.

Food additives or food dyes (E-171, E-173) are substances added to products for technological purposes to give them the necessary properties and qualities during production, packaging, transportation or storage. They are used as certain dyes, flavors, preservatives (Alyakhnovich, N.S., 2015; Alyakhnovich N.S., Novikov D.K., 2016). These dyes are used in the cosmetics industry, in the production of cigarettes, oil, flour, toothpaste, confectionery, chewing gum, candy, fast food, beverages, cheese and many other products, as well as in the pharmaceutical industry. According to the chemical composition, these food additives are E-171 titanium dioxide, E-173 aluminum. According to the chemical composition of these food additives, E-171 is titanium dioxide, and E-173 is aluminum. E-171 - titanium dioxide formula TiO_2 . Titanium dioxide is used in nanotechnology and as a dye and preservative in medical preparations. Because it is a substance resistant to chemicals, it cannot be broken down by the body, has low toxicity, has a biological effect on the body (Bessonov V.V., Perederyaev O.I., Bogachuk M.N., Malinkin A.D., 2012). Some studies have shown that titanium dioxide can cause inflammation in the gut and an increase in free radicals in the tissues, so this substance is stored in the body. This stored substance has the ability to destroy organic particles. Since they are strong moisture retainers, they disrupt the body's water balance. This substance damages both single and double strands of DNA. Thus, it damages chromosomes and disrupts gene structure. Free radicals can damage cells and tissues, increase the risk of developing various diseases such as cancer, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and also accelerate the aging process. Other studies have shown that inhaling titanium dioxide powder can cause lung and body damage. In addition, it was found that this dye makes it difficult to absorb some vitamins and minerals. European food safety regulators

have declared titanium dioxide unsafe for human consumption due to its potential toxicity.

Stomach - This is one of the main organs of the digestive tract. It digests all the food we use. This is due to the hydrochloric acid solution present in the stomach. This chemical compound is released by special cells in the stomach wall. The structure of the stomach is represented by several types of tissues. In addition, cells that secrete hydrochloric acid and other biologically active substances are not located throughout the body. Therefore, anatomically, the stomach consists of several sections. Each of them differs in terms of functionality. Changes in pH, as well as proteins and enzymes under the influence of E-171 and E-173 during digestion have not been sufficiently analyzed in living organisms. There are no biological treatments for the exposure of mice to E-171 and E-173 because how they do it and their harmful effects are not well understood, and extensive research is needed. Changes related to, better analysis of stomach characteristics and coordinated treatment methods should be carried out by comprehensive studies and laboratories. The effect of E-171 and E-173 on rats can be determined using biochemical analysis (Gmoshinsky I.V., Bagryantseva O.V., Khotimchenko S.A., 2019). This test helps determine the composition and amount of chemicals present in rats. Biochemical analysis is very important to identify and record changes in gastric properties.

E173 paints, i.e. give aluminum products a bright silver color. It is used in the production of foil for food. A particularly high concentration of aluminum is observed in canned drinks that are used in the inner packaging of aluminum containers and drinks. There are assumptions that the constant consumption of aluminum in food may be associated with the development of certain diseases, such as Alzheimer's disease, various neurological diseases and allergic reactions. In Russia and Ukraine, the use of the E173 additive in the food industry is prohibited. In addition, E173 dye is banned in Australia and a number of other

countries. While most studies suggest that normal amounts of aluminum in food are not harmful to human health, most of these studies have been conducted in animals or in vitro, and more research is needed to evaluate the effects in humans. Rats can experience morphofunctional changes in the stomach associated with exposure to E-171 and E-173 (Onishchenko G.E., Erokhina M.V., Abramchuk S.S., Shaitan K.V., Raspopov R.V., Smirnova V.V. and others, 2012). E173 means Aluminum enters the body's internal environment through food and various environmental objects. For example, water, food contact materials (packaging materials, cooking utensils), food additives containing aluminum. In the last decade, various toxic effects of aluminum have been discovered, including neurotoxic effects that cause the risk of developing neurodegenerative diseases. Analyzing the consumption of aluminum shows that the minimum amount of aluminum contained in food products containing aluminum should be taken into the human body in a limited amount. (Raspopov R.V., Vernikov V.M., Shumakova A.A, - 2010.)

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